

ISSN (o): 3030-3362

N^o 6 (15)

27.05.2024

Latm. 12/2024

RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION
TADQIQ VA TATBIQ
ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

CERTIFICATE
N^o 078777

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Jurnal oyda bir
marta nashr etiladi.

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiya agentligida
2023-yil 3-mayda
№078777
raqam bilan ro'yxatga
olingan

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THE PROBLEM OF IODINE DEFICIENCY

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Abstract. *The problem of iodine deficiency is extremely important and relevant for many countries. More than 1 billion inhabitants of the earth live in places with a low content of iodine in the biosphere (water, soil, air, food). As a result of this deficiency, 200 million people develop an enlarged thyroid gland (endemic goiter), 20 million develop mental retardation due to insufficient thyroid hormones. It has been established that the high prevalence of endemic goiter among schoolchildren leads to a decrease in cognitive abilities by 15 percent.*

Keywords: *iodine, thyroid gland, mental retardation, World Health Organization, trace element, irritability, depressed mood, drowsiness, lethargy, forgetfulness*

ПРОБЛЕМА ДЕФИЦИТА ЙОДА

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Абстракт. *Проблема дефицита йода чрезвычайно важна и актуальна для многих стран. Более 1 миллиарда жителей Земли проживают в местах с низким содержанием йода в биосфере (вода, почва, воздух, пища). В результате этого дефицита у 200 миллионов человек развивается увеличение щитовидной железы (эндемический зоб), у 20 миллионов развивается умственная отсталость из-за недостаточности гормонов щитовидной железы. Установлено, что высокая распространенность эндемического зоба среди школьников приводит к снижению познавательных способностей на 15 процентов.*

Ключевые слова: *йод, щитовидная железа, умственная отсталость, Всемирная организация здравоохранения, микроэлемент, раздражительность, депрессивное настроение, сонливость, вялость, забывчивость*

According to the World Health Organization, overcoming this problem could be the most significant achievement in world health, surpassing in importance the eradication of smallpox on the globe.

According to medical statistics, now the actual average consumption of iodine by a resident of some regions is 40–80 mcg per day, while the norm is 150–200 mcg. In conditions of such a deficiency of a microelement, the thyroid gland uses the small amount of iodine that is available in the body. At the same time, she has to work several times more intensively and faster, so the volume of the gland increases, a goiter occurs.

In the world, iodine deficiency in nature is one of the main environmental problems, since almost all of its territory is endemic for goiter. The disease occurs on average in 10-15 percent of the urban population. At the same time, our industry meets the demand for iodized salt by no more than 30 percent, and the recommendations of the World Health Organization for the universal iodization of table salt to eliminate the shortage are implemented with great difficulty.

To prevent the consequences of iodine deficiency, the following are used: mass prevention: enrichment with iodine of widely consumed food products; group prophylaxis: prescribing iodine preparations to those who have a special need for iodine (primarily children, adolescents, pregnant and lactating women), as well as individual prophylaxis: this is the administration of iodine preparations in a dose corresponding to the daily physiological need of a person, after consultation with a doctor .

Iodine is one of the most important trace elements necessary for the smooth functioning of the human body. The lack of this microelement is of great concern to physicians around the world. Iodine deficiency is a truly global problem that has affected more than one and a half billion inhabitants of the planet.

In the human body, iodine is contained in negligible amounts: only 20-30 mg, of which about 10 mg is in the thyroid gland. The main role of iodine is participation in the formation of thyroid hormones, however, there is evidence that with a deficiency of this trace element, breast diseases can develop.

And yet the main significance of iodine is that it is an indispensable component of thyroid hormones. There is no such organ or body system that would not need these hormones. They are involved in providing the body with energy, which is needed not only to perform mechanical work, but also for a full-

fledged metabolism, the normal course of biosynthesis processes, the growth and development of the body and the renewal of its tissues. As long as a person receives a sufficient amount of energy, he is alert, full of strength, cheerful and healthy. As soon as at least one of the energy chains fails, the state of health worsens. With serious malfunctions in energy metabolism, a person becomes ill.

Iodine deficiency negatively affects the human condition. It leads to disruption of the synthesis of vital thyroid hormones. At the same time, a feedback mechanism is triggered: a signal is sent to the thyroid gland: "Not enough hormones." Receiving it, the gland begins to increase in volume, trying to compensate for the production of missing hormones due to tissue growth. But this, of course, does not happen, because there is not enough building material - iodine. As a result, endemic goiter develops.

But this is only one aspect of iodine deficiency. In addition, there is a decrease in immunity, therefore, the risk of infectious diseases increases, mental retardation is noted, general weakness is observed, and vision problems arise. And a few years ago, based on studies using modern methods for assessing human intelligence, scientists made a sensational conclusion: iodine deficiency in the first place (long before the outward signs of hypothyroidism develop) hits a person's mental abilities. But there is a fact confirmed by foreign studies: when iodine was added to the diet of children from the control group, intellectual indicators increased by 10-15%.

Prolonged iodine deficiency can cause impaired fertility in women, impaired growth and mental development in children, and a number of other abnormalities.

Often hypothyroidism caused by iodine deficiency occurs in the so-called subclinical form. The person feels normal and is considered healthy. And only with special examinations do we find a decrease in thyroid function. Such a latent course of hypothyroidism is often accompanied by impaired reproductive function: malfunctions in the functioning of the thyroid gland involve the entire endocrine system in the pathological process.

The possibility of a woman becoming pregnant is reduced, there are problems with carrying a pregnancy, the development of the fetus and the child is disturbed. This is a reality, and when women turn to a gynecologist about the

inability to become pregnant or with complaints of abnormal menstruation, tests to assess thyroid function should be included in the general examination.

If we do not take threatening cases, then iodine deficiency makes itself felt by increased fatigue, drowsiness, memory impairment and the ability to concentrate, increased anxiety, and excessive temperature sensitivity. It is also a shame that diseases associated with iodine deficiency primarily threaten those who work a lot and have little rest, are often stressed, eat improperly and irregularly.

Determining that you are deficient in iodine is not very difficult. Many ailments testify to this: thyroid disease, infertility, decreased mental and physical performance, drowsiness, constant constipation, susceptibility to colds, cardiac disorders, hair loss and thinning, brittle nails, obesity, a decrease in the amount of breast milk and the rapid cessation of lactation in nursing women

The main amount of this trace element we consume with food. The highest concentration of iodine is in marine fish and seafood - approximately 800-1000 mg/kg; Seaweeds are especially rich in iodine. There is a lot of iodine in fish oil.

The simplest and most reliable way to prevent iodine deficiency is to use iodized salt. The iodine content in such salt should be $40 \pm 15 \mu\text{g/g}$. If we take into account the norm of daily salt intake by a person, which is 5-6 g, then this amount of iodine will be quite enough to cover daily expenses (100-200 mcg). But remember: in order to preserve a valuable trace element, you need to salt soups or porridge not at the beginning, but at the end of cooking

Or cook everything undersalted, and add salt already in a plate, each according to your taste.

Until now, many people believe that it is possible to enrich the body with iodine using the usual pharmacy solution of iodine. Doctors often encounter burns of the mucous membrane, larynx and esophagus when the patient, having decided to treat the body, used a homemade iodine solution. In most cases, such self-treatment ends with burns. Therefore, it is strictly forbidden to use an alcohol solution of iodine or Lugol as a preventive measure. This is not the iodine that your body lacks.

According to the results of the World Health Organization, the peak of thyroid diseases falls on 2001-2005. Iodine deficiency is especially dangerous in pregnant women. They have an increased risk of having children with low birth

weight, sensorineural deafness, spastic paralysis, cretinism, as well as stillborn babies and miscarriages.

Iodine deficiency negatively affects male potency and mental development of children, which entails the physical and intellectual degeneration of the nation.

Iodine is found in seafood (mussels, oysters, sea kale), but who among ordinary citizens can afford these delicacies in everyday food?

It consists in adding iodine to the most common foods. One of the most affordable and easy to use mineral, drinking and table water enriched with iodine ions

Consequences of iodine deficiency in the body:

- Emotional: Irritability, depressed mood, drowsiness, lethargy, forgetfulness, bouts of inexplicable melancholy, memory and attention impairment, decreased intelligence.

- Cardiological: atherosclerosis resistant to treatment with diet and drugs; arrhythmia, in which the use of special drugs does not give a tangible and lasting effect; an increase in diastolic (lower) pressure due to swelling of the vascular walls.

- Hematological: a decrease in the level of hemoglobin in the blood, in which treatment with iron preparations gives only a modest result

- Immunodeficiency: weakening of the immune system occurs even with a slight decrease in thyroid function, which leads to a decrease in the body's resistance to infectious and colds; weakening, the development of chronic diseases;

- Edema: swelling around the eyes or general, in which the systematic use of diuretics aggravates the condition, forming a dependence on them.

- Gynecological: violation of menstrual function (irregularity sometimes absence of menstruation); infertility, mastopathy; irritation and cracked nipples.

- With a decrease in thyroid function, bone growth slows down, the processes of normal maturation of a growing organism are disturbed.

There are not so many ways to get rid of iodine deficiency - you can take dietary supplements with iodine, add it to food, or breathe air saturated with iodine. In the first two cases, we are talking about the ingestion of iodine into the body through the stomach, but the thing is that the course of the digestive process is very individual. And the success of its replenishment in this way may not be

achieved due to the side mechanisms of the absorption of drugs and the age and constitutional characteristics of human metabolism.

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Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 06 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 06 2024	Том 02. Вып. 06 2024

44. Усмонова, М. А., & Расулова, Ш. А. (2019). Влияние темперамента на деятельность и поведение человека. Вестник науки и образования, (19-3 (73)), 56-58.
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Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 06 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 06 2024	Том 02. Вып. 06 2024

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tahririyat manzili:

150100, Farg‘ona vil., Farg‘ona sh., Solim ko‘chasi, 23/4-uy, 26-xonadon

E-mail:

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“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali "Fer-Teach" MChJ muassisligida tashkil etilgan bo‘lib, ilmiy va uslubiy jihatdan Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Farg'ona filiali tomonidan qo‘llab-quvvatlanadi. Mazkur jurnal O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan 2023-yil 3-mayda ommaviy axborot vositasi sifatida davlat ro‘yxatidan (№ 078777) o‘tkazilgan.

ISSN 3030-3362.

Jurnal aniq va tabiiy fanlar, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy fanlar, texnika fanlari, tibbiyot fanlari, pedagogika fanlari sohalarini qamrab oladi. Tahrir hay‘ati a‘zolidan respublikaning turli OTMLarida faoliyat olib boruvchi fan nomzodlari va doktorlari o‘rin olishgan..

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Научно-методический журнал “Исследования и внедрение”

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Учредителем научно-технического журнала

«Исследования и внедрение» является ООО “Fer-Teach”.

Журнал издается с 2023 года, зарегистрирован 3 мая 2023 года Агентством информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации Президента Республики Узбекистан (Сертификат № 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

«Исследования и внедрение» является специализированным журналом в области техники и охватывает все основные направления исследований и разработок в различных областях технических наук: физике, математике, информационных технологиях. В журнале также публикуются научные статьи по лингвистике, методике преподавания и истории развития технических наук.

Языки издания: Узбекский, русский, английский и каракалпакский

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 06 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 06 2024	Том 02. Вып. 06 2024

Scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation”

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150100, Fergana region, Fergana, Solim street, building 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Our website:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

The scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation” was founded by Fer-Teach LLC and supported by the Fergana branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi. This journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023 (No 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

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